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Il lupo (*Canis lupus*) in Romania: ecologia alimentare invernale e interazione spaziale con la lince (*Lynx lynx*)

Relatore

Marco Zaccaroni

Correlatore

Andrea Gazzola

Correlatore

Viorel D. Popescu

Candidato

Andrea Corradini

to Simona

WOLF (*Canis lupus*) IN ROMANIA: WINTER FEEDING ECOLOGY AND SPATIAL INTERACTION WITH LYNX (*Lynx lynx*)

SUPPORTED BY:

CONTENTS

Abstract	1
Introduction.....	2
Study area.....	4
CHAPTER 1 - WINTER DIET OF WOLF (<i>CANIS LUPUS</i>)	
Materials and Methods	7
Scat collection	8
Laboratory analysis.....	8
Scat analysis methods	9
Wild ungulate abundance	10
Statistical analysis.....	11
Results	12
Discussion.....	17
Scat collection	17
Scat analysis methods	18
Wolf diet - Ungulates.....	18
Wolf diet - Other prey species.....	21
CHAPTER 2 - WINTER SPATIAL INTERACTION BETWEEN WOLF (<i>CANIS LUPUS</i>) AND LYNX (<i>LYNX LYNX</i>)	
Materials and Methods	23
Snow-tracking survey	24
Habitat selection	24
Temporal and spatial overlap.....	26
Results	27
Discussion.....	31
Snow-tracking survey	31
Habitat selection	31
Altitude selection	32
Species overlap.....	33
Acknowledgements	35
References.....	36
Annexes	45

ABSTRACT

ITA: Il lupo (*Canis lupus*) è probabilmente una delle specie animali più studiate in Europa. Ad oggi, nonostante i numerosi lavori condotti sul predatore, poche ricerche sono state effettivamente realizzate nei Carpazi Rumeni. Questo studio, svolto all'interno del progetto WOLFLIFE (LIFE13 NAT/RO/000205), ha come scopo quello di valutare il ruolo ecologico del lupo in Romania, analizzando la sua dieta invernale e l'interazione spaziale con la lince Euroasiatica (*Lynx lynx*). Eseguita durante l'inverno 2014/15, la raccolta dei segni di presenza è stata realizzata tramite l'esecuzione di transetti, sia standard che occasionali, su un'area di 1.200 km². Per valutare la dieta del lupo sono stati analizzati 135 escrementi di lupo selezionati da un campione totale di 270 escrementi. Fra tutte le categorie alimentari trovate, il cinghiale (*Sus scrofa*) ha rappresentato la principale specie preda durante tutto l'inverno, rappresentando il 57,9% della biomassa ingerita, seguito dal capriolo (*Capreolus capreolus*) e dal cervo (*Cervus elaphus*), rispettivamente al 20% e al 13,6%. Il cane (*Canis familiaris*) ha rappresentato con il 5,2% la quarta specie in ordine d'importanza. Le piste d'impronte dei due predatori collezionate durante l'attività di snow tracking hanno permesso di calcolare sia il grado di sovrapposizione spaziale e temporale dei due carnivori che l'uso dell'habitat (copertura del suolo ed elevazione). Le specie hanno mostrato un uso simile dell'habitat e del territorio a livello spaziale ma non temporale, suggerendo che i due carnivori usano gli stessi luoghi ma in momenti diversi.

Parole chiave: lupo; dieta; lince; interazione spaziale; Romania; WOLFLIFE.

ENG: The grey wolf (*Canis lupus*) is probably one of the most studied species in Europe. To date, despite the large number of projects that have been addressed to it, few studies have actually been carried out in the Romanian Carpathian. This pioneering study, entirely developed within the WOLFLIFE project (LIFE13 NAT/RO/000205), aimed to assess the ecological role of the predator in Romania, studying its winter feeding ecology and the spatial interaction with the Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*). Accomplished during the winter 2014/15, the collection of signs of presence was achieved by performing transects, both standard and occasional, over an area of 1.200 km². In total, from 270 excrements collected, 135 were selected and analysed to assess the wolf diet. Out of all food types found (n=12), wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) represented the main preyed species throughout the winter, accounting for 57,9% of biomass ingested, followed by roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*) and red deer (*Cervus elaphus*) at 20% and 13,6%, respectively. Dog (*Canis familiaris*) ranked fourth accounting for 5,2%. Regarding the species interaction, the overlap of the signs of presence for both species was compared, based on snow tracking data and considering variables such as land cover and elevation. Despite a similar use in habitat and altitude, the species share their territory spatially but not temporally, suggesting that both carnivores share the same trails but use them at different times.

Keywords: wolf; diet; lynx; spatial interaction; Romania; WOLFLIFE.

INTRODUCTION

The study of a ubiquitous species in a new environmental context represents a major step to enhance the knowledge of its role in the ecosystem. Although wolf ecology has been largely surveyed over the world (Mech & Boitani, 2003), so far there are still regions where it has been poorly investigated, Romania definitely being one of these. With one of the largest (Kaczensky et al, 2013) and yet most understudied wolf populations in Europe, the country represents an important area in which to explore the ecology of this carnivore. Characteristics emphasized by the peculiarities of the area, where the presence of three large carnivores is combined with a very low human density. Furthermore, being an umbrella species (Ripple et al, 2014), the wolf should be of priority importance when planning research. The maintenance of a viable population is, in fact, essential to preserve not only the species but the whole ecosystem (Ripple et al, 2014). This study, carried out by the WOLFLIFE project and developed in the Eastern Carpathian Mountains, aimed to investigate the current role of the wolf in Romania, focusing on its winter diet and the spatial interaction with lynx (*Lynx lynx*).

Historically numerous across the whole of Romania, the wolf population decreased dramatically, as in most of Europe, after World War II (Jędrzejewska et al, 1996; Kaczensky et al, 2013; Sin et al, 2014). Nearly extinct in the 1960s, a series of socio-economical changes occurred concurrently with the rise to power of Nicolae Ceaușescu (from 1965), allowed a slow but steady increment in numbers (Sin et al, 2014), avoiding extirpation which took place in other EU nations due to human persecution, habit loss and decline in prey (Wilson & Millermeier, 2009). The population decreased once again after the fall of the dictator in 1989, but this second time not as alarmingly as thirty years before (Sin et al, 2014). After these recent fluctuations, it is now considered stable, with an estimated number of 2.300 – 2.700 individuals (Kaczensky et al, 2013), though this is number is disputed (WolfLife, unpublished data).

Despite wolf feeding ecology being studied in Eurasia since the 1950s (Korneev, 1950; Mertz, 1953; Gavrin & Donaurov, 1954), only a little research has been undertaken since then in Romania (Almasan et al, 1970; Ionescu, 1993; Sin et al, 2015). A remarkable, opportunistic carnivore (Peterson & Ciucci, 2003), the wolf is capable of hunting prey from 1 kg (snowshoe hare) to 1.000 kg (bison), feeding, as necessary, on a wide range of food resources such as livestock, fish, fruit and even garbage (Peterson & Ciucci, 2003). Except in areas with poor ecological conditions (Macdonald et al, 1980; Meriggi et al, 1991; Singh and Kumara, 2006), wild ungulates represent the bulk of the wolf diet throughout Northern Hemisphere (Peterson & Ciucci, 2003). In order to understand the feeding ecology of the Romanian wolf, the first part of the study sought to quantify this issue. Conducted over the winter 2014/15 using the most reliable techniques proposed in the literature (Ciucci et al, 1996; Klare et al, 2011), the diet was characterized considering the prey availability in the study area.

The wolf shares its environment with many animals besides those that they prey on. The nature of these interactions may vary considerably depending on the species engaged: a common interaction generally involves the ecological guild, a group of species using common resources in a similar way (Root, 1967), in the case of wolf represented by the lynx and the bear (*Ursus arctos*). As Romania is one of the few nations in EU where the large carnivore community is widespread (Kaczensky et al, 2013), the study area represented a de facto ecological hotspot where the intraguild interactions could be studied. In the second part of this study, the research focused thus on the spatial interaction between wolf and lynx, not considering the bear (virtually missing because of the hibernation period). Sympatric species across the vast Palearctic area (IUCN, 2015), the two species have regularly shared the Romanian territory for centuries. However, the information reported in the literature regarding their interspecific relationships is often contradictory. For example, in Russia and Fennoscandia the coexistence of the two large carnivores was often characterized by negative influences of wolf on lynx (see review in Schmidt et al, 2009). Conversely, in other areas the two species coexist without apparent reciprocal influence (Jedrzejewska and Jedrzejewski 1998; Schmidt et al, 2009; Wikenros et al, 2010; Krofel et al, 2012; Kusak et al, 2013). Although the interactions may occur at multiple scales (Ballard et al, 2003), in this particular case, interaction was considered by investigating the habitat/altitude selection by both predators and their spatial and temporal overlap.

Being a pioneering study, the measurement of both habitat use and food habits was done using resource selection indexes (Manly et al, 2002). A measure of niche size and dietary preference, resource selection is driven by a number of factors such as population density, competition with other species, natural selection, heredity, habitat patch size and inter-patch distances (Peek, 1986). Several models and theories of resource selection have been proposed over the years, including foraging models and habitat selection models (see review in Manly et al, 2002). Despite their better accuracy in explaining phenomenon, in this study attention was restricted to statistical techniques for the detection and measurement of the degree to which a resource is selected or avoided (Manly et al, 2002). This complete thesis has been done following the useful and constructive guideline proposed by Day (1998).

STUDY AREA

Conducted in the Eastern Romanian Carpathians mountains (45° 58'N - 26° 26'E), the WOLFLIFE project study area included six different counties (Mureș, Harghita, Neamț, Bacău, Covasna and Vrancea) and eighteen SCI (Site of Community Importance). Due to the large scale of the project (34.437 km²), the project was focused on five study areas (Figure 1), among which Putna-Vrancea-Soveja-Oituz (PVSO) was selected as first study area (1.200 km²) (Figure 2). The whole study areas were defined by squares of 10x10 km from EEA reference grid (EEA, 2011).

The characteristics of the study areas were established following these guidelines:

- the EEA reference grid was used in agreement with EU policy on facilitating and standardizing the management at European scale (Annoni, 2004).
- the surface of the study areas (ranging from 600 to 1.200 km²) was set according to Boitani & Powell (2012), which suggest, “*Due to large individual home-ranges (...), researchers need to conduct surveys over large enough areas to produce biologically and statistically meaningful results*”. Having the wolf, in these latitudes, home-ranges from 100-200 km² (Potvin, 1988; Wydeven et al, 1995; Findo & Chovancová, 2004; Kusak et al, 2005; Jędrzejewski et al, 2007), we considered an area in which potentially 3-6 packs could live.
- as Boitani & Powell (2012) suggested, an adequate monitoring “*... require data to be collected systematically in space and time, through precise sampling protocols.*” According to the objectives of the project, and being the sampling effort transect-based (Campbell et al, 2008), the squares were primarily used to spread equally the effort (temporally and spatially) in the study areas.
- according to the *stratification* approach, the squares selection was made in the areas where it had assumed a higher probability of large carnivore detection, thus avoiding a low sampling efficiency and waste of resources (Boitani & Powell, 2012). Moreover, the study areas were selected to have a representative sample of the whole project area in terms of land cover, landscape features, human density and administrative/ jurisdictional boundaries (SCI and counties).

The PVSO includes two SCI: the *Putna-Vrancea Natural Park* (382 km²), a protected area instituted in 2004 which it is both Site of Community Importance (ROSCI208 - Putna Vrancea) and Special Faunistic Protected Areas (ROSPA0088 - Vrancea Mountains), and the SCI site *Oituz – Ojdula* (152,7 km² - ROSCI0130), instituted in 2007 (EEA, 2005). Alpine biogeographical region, in PVSO the altitude ranges from 400 to 1.777 m above sea level, characterized by certain features of a continental climate but with higher average precipitation than the surrounding plains. Precipitation vary from 1.000 to 1.500 mm, with cold winters and hot summers (EEA, 2002). Snow cover varies considerably depending on altitude, ranging from November-December to April-May.

With some of Europe's largest stands of virgin forest, the area is characterized by a great variety of tree species, with distribution patterns corresponding to the various altitudinal belts. Covered mostly by forest (85% of the study area) (Figure 8), lowlands and hills are dominated by both English oak (*Quercus robur*) and Irish oak (*Quercus petraea*), while in the mid-mountain, sycamore maple (*Acer pseudoplatanus*), European ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*), Scots elm (*Ulmus glabra*) and small-leaved lime (*Tilia cordata*) are found it. At upper levels, mixed forests of beech-fir or beech-fir-spruce (*Fagus sylvatica*, *Abies alba* and *Picea abies*) form the 53% of the whole forests. European larch (*Larix decidua*), dwarf mountain pine (*Pinus mugo*) and Swiss pine (*Pinus Cembra*) are also present in the area (EEA, 2002).

The large mammal community is composed of grey wolf (*Canis lupus*), Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) (Figure 9), brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) (Figure 10), wild boar (*Sus scrofa*), roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus*), red deer (*Cervus elaphus*) and Carpathian chamois (*Rupicapra rupicapra carpatica*). Stray dogs are also present in the area, mostly close to human settlement during the winter, in summer, due to shepherding activity, they are found from the valleys to the highest portions of the study area. Both wolf and bear are legally hunted in Romania. Lynx, after Romania entered in the EU (in 2007), it became strictly protected (Pop et al, 2013).

The PVS0 area included nine villages (Poiana Sărată, Oituz, Scutaru, Lepșa, Greșu, Ghelița, Ojdula, Mărtănuș, Brețcu) wherein live 12.612 people (INS, 2011a). With a population density of 10,5 people/km², concentrated mainly in the boroughs, the human settlements constitute only the 0,06 % of the entire study area (INS, 2011b). The road network is limited and partially in poor condition. A national road (2D) cross the whole area and two others (2L and 11), pass through it more peripherally. However, due to the widespread logging activity, numerous forest roads are present in the territory. Sheep farming and logging activity are the main economic activities in the study area. Strictly seasonal the first (only in summer), logging activities continue throughout the whole year.

FIGURE 1 – WOLFLIFE project area and the five study areas (top left in blue). © WOLFLIFE

FIGURE 2– The Putna-Vrancea-Soveja-Oituz (PVS) study area

- CHAPTER 1 -

WINTER DIET OF WOLF (*Canis lupus*)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SCAT COLLECTION

Due to the unknown distribution of wolves and the number of packs in the study area, the scat selection was made according to a specific experimental design, conceived to distribute the collection equally in terms of space and time. Spatially, the EEA reference grid (EEA, 2011) was used to spread uniformly the collection across the PVSO. Temporally, within the winter season (from November 2014 to April 2015), the reference period was divided in three bimesters (Nov.-Dec. / Jan.-Feb. / Mar.-Apr.), each of which was used as *survey period*. A minimum period of two months was chosen to give the possibility at the predator to depose again in the area (not wasting costly effort).

Every square was systematically covered by feet with a minimum of 20 km of transect each bimester (standard effort), plus some occasional transects where few scats were found or more information was needed. Transects were designed to maximize the samples encounter. Wolf excrements (Figure 11) were searched in areas where the probability to detect them was higher (hiking trails, forest roads, ridges, paths, etc.) and by following wolf tracks in the snow. Scat discrimination between wolf and dog was done considering a conservative multicriteria approach (Ciucci et al, 1996). The excrement content (e.g. anthropogenic food, garbage, etc), the location (e.g. near to a village, a sheepfold, logger's hut, etc) as well as the volume and the general aspect (e.g. scats with diameter < 30 mm, as suggested by Weaver & Fritts, 1979 and Reed et al, 2004, with unusual shape, etc) were regarded as primary factors to discard the sample. The month of deposition was estimated considering the general aspect of the scat, the weather conditions, exposure of deposition site and other factors that may potentially affect the scat appearance (Ciucci et al, 1996). Thus excrements were classified into three categories (Fresh = $t < 1$ week; Medium = $t \leq 1$ month; Old = $t > 1$ month), and once classed, the deposition month was assigned considering the collection day. Once it was identified as wolf sample and the age was established, the excrement was collected in a nylon bag, labelled with a univocal code and georeferenced with a handheld Global Positioning System (Garmin GPS 64s).

To better understand the wolf distribution, all signs of presence (tracks, urines, scratches, etc.) were collected during the field survey. Data storage was done using DNRgps 6.1.0.6 (Minnesota Department of Natural Resources, 2015) and Microsoft Excel 2013. All the spatial analyses were conducted with QGIS 2.8.1 "Wien" (QGIS Development Team, 2015).

LABORATORY ANALYSIS

Laboratory procedures followed, with some adjustments, the protocol proposed by Reynolds & Aebischer (1991) and Ciucci et al (1996). First, prepared the equipment and prior to washing, all sample were associated with a lab form (Figure 6) in order to avoid

loss of information during flushing procedure and thus speed up the process. After catalogued, each scat was soaked for 15-20 minutes in a plastic basin with water and detergent (Figure 12). Manually broken, it was washed with running water for several minutes through a sieve with 0,5 mm mesh, in order to divide micro (< 0,5 mm) and macro-components (> 0,5 mm) of each sample (Reynolds & Aebischer, 1991). Once rinsed, the remains were soaked again in order to divide, by decantation, light materials (such as hairs) to heavier parts (such as bones, hooves, claws or teeth). Floating items were first picked up using forceps and deposited it in a plastic container, then bones and other remains were added. All the remains of little or no nutritive value, ingested both intentionally (e.g. *Poaceae*) or involuntarily by the wolf (e.g. leaves, soil, stones, etc.), were excluded from the analysis (Ciucci et al, 1996). Left to dry at room temperature, once it was dried, the sample was bagged in a sealed bag and the related lab form was stapled with it (Figure 13).

The mammalian hair examination was made following a stepwise procedure, in order to classify the sample first macroscopically and gradually get to the microscopic level. The operation was made as follows:

- 1) by eyes, it was examined the colour, length, corrugation and diameter.
- 2) by a 10x lens, it was examined the texture, opacity and banding.
- 3) by a 100x/400x stereoscopic microscope, it was examined, in a slide, the cuticula and medulla.

Comparison of hair features was made with identification keys (Teerink, 1991; De Marinis & Asprea, 2006; Lombardi & Ragni, 2011), as well as using an online photographic gallery (MicrolabNW, 2007) and collections of hairs picked both locally and at the National Museum of Natural History of “Grigore Antipa” (Bucharest).

To distinguish cervid species (red deer and roe deer), a large number of hair samples from different parts of the body were used. Hooves/claws, teeth and bones were also used to determine the consumed prey. When the classification by species was impossible, the highest certain taxonomic order (e.g. family – *Cervidae*) was assigned. Plant residues were considered as “Vegetable”. The samples that were impossible to classify were sorted as “Indeterminate”. No blind test was done (Ciucci et al, 1996), however, to improve the observer abilities, a training session was performed before the scat analysis.

SCAT ANALYSIS METHODS

Considering the different scat analysis methods recommended in the literature to assess the wolf diet, for the aim of this study, were taken into account only three of them, following the guidelines proposed by Ciucci et al (1996) and Klare (2011). Complementary methods, the results of each should be interpreted separately since each analysis present both positive and negative aspects. Pooled together, however, they provide a general information on wolf food habits. The used methods were:

A) *Frequency of occurrence* (OCC)

Qualitative method expressed as *the percentage of the number of occurrences of one food item of the total number of occurrences of all food items* (Klare, 2011). It was calculated as follows:

$$f_i = \frac{n_i}{N} = \frac{n_i}{\sum n_{i,j,\dots}}$$

where f_i is the frequency of occurrence, n_i the number of occurrence of food item i and N the total number occurrences of all food items i, j, \dots in the sample. As suggested by Ciucci et al (1996), to partially reduce the frequency overestimation of small prey, foods in trace amounts were not taken into considered (< 5% of relative volume).

B) *Relative volumes of remains* (VOL)

Quantitative method, the relative volume was visually estimated overlaying each scat remain with a reference grid, expressing the different content as percentage of volume (Ciucci et al, 1996). In detail, five different categories were assigned based on the relative presence: < 5% (*trace*, not considered in the analysis), 6-25%, 26-50%, 51-75% and 76-100% (as described in Mattioli et al, 1995). Thus, all the relative volumes of a given food items were summed and subsequently used in the biomass calculation.

C) *Biomass ingested* (BIO)

Quantitative method, it was developed from a controlled environment (wolves in captivity) to study the relationship between prey biomass consumed per collectable scat produced. The following linear regression model explained the biomass model:

$$y = 0,439 + 0,008x, \quad r^2 = 0,78$$

where y is the biomass ingested per collectable scat and x , the independent variable, the live weight (expressed in kg) of a given prey (Weaver, 1993). Live weight of prey species were taken from the literature (Blanchard, 1987; Serafini & Lovari, 1993; Ciucci et al, 1996; Głowaciński & Profus, 1997; Oklahoma State University, 2002; Mattioli et al, 2011).

WILD UNGULATE ABUNDANCE

Wild ungulate abundance in PVS0 was extrapolated by pellet group count survey (WolfLife, unpublished data) (Figure 14). Based on the cited reference grid (EEA, 2011), the survey was carried out by WolfLife working team between May and June 2015, when the area was no longer covered by snow. Performed on strip transects, the effort was equally distributed in each surveyed square. Throughout the study area, the community of wild ungulates was composed by roe deer (34,90%), red deer (32,36%), wild boar (30,16%) and chamois (2,58%). Being the study developed in the WolfLife project, the full methodology applied and the data will be released according to the project timetable.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

A resample with replacement (Bootstrapping) was calculated to assess the effect of random sampling error (Manly, 1998). Following the procedure suggested by Reynolds & Aebischer (1991), a new sample as large as the analyzed one was randomly selected from the database and the diet composition (namely the OCC, VOL and BIO) was determined. The procedure was repeated 1.000 times and the 95% confidence limits of each food item was calculated. The same computation was performed in all bimester, but only for the biomass ingested.

Ivlev's index of selectivity (modified by Jacobs, 1974) was calculated to assess wolf selectivity on wild ungulates:

$$D = \frac{(r_i - p_i)}{(r_i + p_i - 2r_i p_i)}$$

where D is the Ivlev's index of electivity, r the proportion of a given prey species i in wolf diet and p the proportion in the free-living population. The result ranges between -1 (total avoidance) through zero (selection proportional to occurrence) to $+1$ (maximum positive selection). Ivlev's selectivity index was calculated considering the prey biomass. The breadth of the food niche was calculated after Levins (1968):

$$B = \frac{1}{\sum p_i^2}$$

where B is the Levins' measure of niche breadth and p_i the proportion of each prey group used by the wolf in terms of biomass. Organized into five categories, wolf food items were grouped as follow: wild ungulates, livestock, large carnivores, meso-mammals and rodents. The Niche breadth is a parameter that attempts to measure how specialized or unspecialized a species is within a given environment. Specialist species will have a much smaller niche breadth (e.g. $B \sim 1$, strong specialization to one group) than a generalist one (e.g. $B \sim 5$, preying on all available groups of food items).

The Log likelihood ratio (G-test) test of independence (Sokal & Rohlf, 1981; Hurd, 2001) was used to statistically test the difference among bimester, as well as the selective predation on the ungulate community. All statistical analysis were carried out with R 3.0.3 "Warm puppy" (R core team, 2014).

RESULTS

In total, 83 transects were performed during the reference season, covering a total length of 869,25 km, with 119 consecutive days of snow cover out of 179 total days of monitoring. Due to prohibitive climatic and logistical conditions (Figure 15), the south-central part of PVS0 (10kmE558N266) was not opportunely covered during the winter. Eventually, out of twelve squares, eleven were properly monitored with the minimum effort established of 20 km per square. In total, 270 scats were collected in PVS0 area during the winter period. According to the deposition months, however, only 183 were suitable for the winter diet, of which 45 from Nov.-Dec., 49 from Jan.-Feb. and 91 from Mar.-Apr. Following the proposed experimental design, a random sample of 45 excrements was selected from each bimester to a total final sample of 135 (Figure 3).

FIGURE 3 – The distribution of transects, scats collected and $KAI_{WolfSigns}$ values (Kilometric Abundance Index of all wolf signs collected) during the winter 2014/15 in PVS0 area. The square codes (e.g. 10KM E557 N269) are shown in the grid.

The relative importance of food items identified is presented below (Table 1). Among the wolf scat collected in the PVS0 area, wild ungulate predominated the winter diet according to all scat analysis methods, representing the 78,5 % of OCC, 81,2 % of VOL and 91,5 % of BIO. The wild boar, independently of the used method, represented the main prey species consumed by wolf during the reference period, accounting for the 44 % of OCC, 48 % of VOL and 57,9 % of BIO. The roe deer appeared right after with the 27 % of OCC, 25,2 % of VOL and 20 % of BIO. The red deer, even if represented the third species in term of VOL and BIO (8 % and 13,6 %, respectively), was listed fourth in terms of OCC (7,5 %), slightly after the dog (8,8 %). The latter species was the last notable food item in the diet representing the 6,7 % of VOL and 5,2 % of BIO. The others species were only sporadic or marginally important. Pooled together (N=14), they reached only 7 % of OCC and 6,3 % of VOL. Due to ambiguous classificatory features, six food items were listed Indeterminate (3,8 % OCC and 3,7 % VOL). Nevertheless, food items at lower ranks had quite wide confidence intervals due to the effect of random sampling error (Graph 1), making the ultimate classification difficult and potentially ambiguous.

Food item	Prey biomass (kg)	Scat analysis methods					
		Frequency of occurrence		Relative volume		Biomass	
		N	%	Σ%	%	kg	%
Wild boar	66 (a)	70	44,0	6.475	48,0	61,97	57,9
Roe deer	24 (b)	43	27,0	3.400	25,2	21,45	20,0
Red deer	115 (b)	12	7,5	1.075	8,0	14,61	13,6
Dog	22 (c)	14	8,8	900	6,7	5,54	5,2
Pig	185 (e)	1	0,6	100	0,7	1,92	1,8
Bear (cub)	23 (d)*	1	0,6	100	0,7	0,62	0,6
<i>Mustelidae</i>	0,7 (f)	2	1,3	200	1,5	0,89	0,8
<i>Rodentia</i>	0,25 (c)	2	1,3	25	0,2	0,11	0,1
<i>Cervidae</i>	/	3	1,9	300	2,2	/	/
<i>Canidae</i>	/	3	1,9	250	1,9	/	/
Vegetables	/	2	1,3	175	1,3	/	/
Indeterminate	/	6	3,8	500	3,7	/	/
Total		159	100	13.500	100	107,11	100

TABLE 1 – Winter diet composition of wolf in the Eastern Carpathians (PVS0 area), Romania in 2014/15 (from Ciucci et al, 1996, modified). (a) Głowaciński & Profus, 1997; (b) Mattioli et al, 2011; (c) Ciucci et al, 1996; (d) Blanchard, 1987; (e) Oklahoma State University, 2002; (f) Serafini & Lovari, 1993; * Despite age classes are not considered, being certainly a young animal, a live weight from that age class was used.

GRAPH 1 – Winter diet composition of wolf and food item relative frequencies in the Eastern Carpathians (PVSO area), Romania in 2014/15 according to all methodologies used (Frequency of occurrence – OCC; Relative volume – VOL; Biomass ingested – BIO). The 95% confidence limits for each frequency are shown.

Statistically there were no significant difference on the prey species ranking (Nov.- Dec. vs Jan.-Feb.: $G = 1,3514$, $df = 3$, $p\text{-value} > 0,5$; Nov.-Dec. vs Mar.-Apr.: $G = 0,8468$, $df = 3$, $p\text{-value} > 0,5$; Jan.-Feb. vs Mar.-Apr.: $G = 2,993$, $df = 3$, $p\text{-value} > 0,5$). The wild boar, steadily ranked at the high position through the whole winter, can be considered of primary importance for the wolf (Table 2). Less certain was the ranking of the other prey species; the large confidence interval (Graph 2; Table 2) suggested indeed to take the results with caution.

	Nov.-Dec.			Jan.-Feb.			Mar.-Apr.		
	%BIO	,025	,975	%BIO	,025	,975	%BIO	,025	,975
Wild Boar	0,59	0,43	0,76	0,61	0,49	0,77	0,54	0,41	0,73
Roe deer	0,19	0,09	0,20	0,17	0,09	0,28	0,24	0,14	0,40
Red deer	0,14	0,03	0,27	0,18	0,07	0,31	0,08	0	0,21
Dog	0,07	0,02	0,15	0,02	0	0,05	0,07	0,02	0,16

TABLE 2- Winter diet composition of wolf among bimester in PVS0, Romania in 2014/15. In the table the relative frequency of biomass ingested and the 95% confidence interval are shown.

GRAPH 2 – Winter diet composition of wolf among bimester in PVS0, Romania in 2014/15. The biomass ingested (BIO) was assessed only for the main prey species. The 95% confidence intervals of each food item are shown.

The Ivlev's indexes of selectivity showed that wolf during the winter 2014/15, despite the wild ungulate population structure in the study area, did not choose its preys according to their availability ($G = 41,4644$, $df = 3$, $p\text{-value} = p\text{-value} < 0,0001$). The wild boar was positively selected ($D = +0,59$), the roe deer was selected to a lesser extent ($D = +0,32$) and red deer was strongly avoided ($D = -0,76$). Chamois, even if sporadically present in the study area, was not found at all during the analysis, showing a total avoidance by the wolf ($D = -1$) (Graph 3). No data on dog consistency was available, making it impossible the wolf selectivity on this species.

GRAPH 3 – Wolf prey selectivity in PVS0, Romania in 2014/15, calculated considering the prey biomass available (from the free-living population, based on pellet group count data) and the prey biomass used (from wolf winter diet).

In the PVS0, according to the niche breadth, wolf showed a strong specialization on wild ungulates out of five different prey groups ($B = 1,17$). The wild ungulates alone represented the 91 % of biomass ingested while the other groups showed to be marginal in the wolf feeding ecology (Table 3).

Food category	Prey species	% Biomass	Niche Breadth (B)
Wild ungulates	wild boar, roe deer, red deer, chamois	91,15	1,17
Livestock	pig	1,8	
Large-carnivores	bear, dog	5,8	
Meso-mammals *	<i>Mustelidae</i>	0,8	
Rodents	rodents	0,1	

TABLE 3 – Food categories and species considered in each group for the calculation of the niche breadth. The biomass is relative to each food category. * Meso-mammals are those larger than a rodent up to roughly fox sized mammals (*Vulpes* spp.) (Hoffmann et al, 2010).

DISCUSSION

SCAT COLLECTION

Spatially, despite the area was covered repeatedly and uniformly during the whole winter, in some squares, few scats were actually collected. According to all signs of presence gathered during the winter 2014/15, it seems that the small number of samples found in some portions of the PVS0, most likely reflect an effective low density of the predator. Considering the higher number of signs of presence found in the Northern and Southeastern parts of PVS0 during the previous year of monitoring (Sin, unpublished data) and being all the area potentially suitable, the uneven wolf distribution was probably affected by a number of reasons such as climate, hunting, topography of the area or even natural population fluctuation. First, regarding the climatic conditions, the winter 2014/15 was considerably snowier than the previous one ([World Weather Online, 2015](#)). Wolves might have gone at the lower altitude or outside the study area, as they might have followed the prey species in other zones ([Fuller et al, 2003](#)). Second, the hunting pressure on wolf may have been high, both from legal and illegal hunting ([Liberg et al, 2012](#)), leading the species to local decrement. Third, the Southeastern part of the study area (characterized by a long steep valley) may have been not suitable for the predator since the available resources, the wild ungulates, may have been scarce during the reference winter. Fourth, the species might have gone through a natural fluctuation. Moreover, due to the considerable altitude of 10kmE558N266 square (reaching 1.780m a.s.l.), the uncovered square was, most likely, marginally used by wolves. Overall, there was the reason to believe that the collected sample was actually representative of the study area. Temporally, with 45 scats per bimester, the sampling was successfully fractionated in terms of time.

Using the genetic analysis of a subsample of scats collected during the reference winter (n=84), no other species, rather than wolf, were detected in PVS0 ([Jarausich & Nowak, 2015](#)). This finding supported the goodness of the data since a potential bias and, therefore, misleading conclusions may be associated with an incorrect sampling ([Marucco et al, 2008](#); [Weiskopf et al, 2016](#)).

Regarding the sample size, the suggestions proposed by [Trites & Joy \(2005\)](#) were regarded as discriminating factors to consider the analyzed sample of 135 scats acceptable for the study. However, though the wild boar steadily occurred at the first rank in all the proposed methods, it appeared to be inadequate to estimate the relative importance of the other food items. The large confidence interval did not allow to weigh the relevance of secondary preys, as for example for the dog, leaving a certain degree of uncertainty in the final conclusions. Same considerations were made regarding the utilization among bimester, in which the used sample size (N= 45) might be lacking in statistical power on detect differences among survey periods. Nevertheless, given the nature of this study, the result was completely achieved, clearly showing the high

utilization of the wild ungulates and the constant use of the wild boar through the whole winter.

SCAT ANALYSIS METHODS

The qualitative methods, such as frequency of occurrence (OCC), tend to overestimate the importance of small food items (Weaver, 1993). Although the method biases and limitations are well explained by several authors (Reynolds & Aebischer, 1991; Weaver, 1993; Ciucci et al, 1996; Klare et al, 2011), the OCC method was used to compare the presented findings with the present literatures, since it is the most used method to assess the diet of wolf (Okarma, 1995; Peterson & Ciucci, 2003; Klare et al, 2011; Zlatanova et al, 2014). Nevertheless, the bimestrial diets, the prey selectivity and the niche breadth were assessed using the biomass ingested, considered it a more reliable method. Similar problems as for the frequency of occurrence method arise using the relative volumes of remains (VOL), although to a lesser extent (Ciucci et al, 1996). The VOL method was primarily used both to discard items occurring in a scat in trace amount (< 5%) and subsequently to assess the biomass ingested. The biomass ingested (BIO), despite some restrictions (Weaver, 1993), is biologically the most meaningful method and it provide the best approximation of the actual wolf diet (Ciucci et al, 1996; Klare et al, 2011). A quantitative method, it allows dealing with the live weight of the prey, pointing out the relative importance of food items with respect to their overall contribution to wolf diet (Floyd et al, 1978).

Being the diet based on scats it was not possible to integrate and improve the BIO analysis with the information suggested by Ciucci et al (1996). Field data such as the prey condition, degree of prey consumption by wolves and the amount of prey lost to scavengers are only feasible in a certain condition and using carcasses. On the contrary, although it would have been achievable to define the prey age classes from hairs (i.e. in winter only from wild boar), the total absence of live weight data by age group class made it impossible this kind of analysis.

WOLF DIET - UNGULATES

Although it is premature to define a specialization (Sinclair et al, 2003) on a specific food item in PVS0 study area, in the reference period wolf fed almost exclusively on wild ungulates (Table 3), selecting wild boar as main prey during all winter, both seasonally and bimonthly (Table 1 & Table 2). The cervids were found to be important too, accounting for one-third of the whole diet, independently to the used method. The wild boar, even if generally accounted as second preyed species in the Palearctic areas after the red deer (Okarma 1995; Zlatanova et al, 2014), it is widely used in a number of countries such as Belarus (Sidorovich et al, 2003), Bulgaria (Genov et al, 2010) Estonia (Kübarsepp & Valdmann, 2003), Italy (Ciucci et al, 1996; Meriggi & Lovari, 1996; Mattioli et al, 2011), Latvia (Anderson, 2003), Spain (Telleria & Saez-Royuela, 1989) and Russia

(Litvinov, 1981). Due to the high climatic, environmental and ecological differences among these countries, the explanation of why the wild boar represent the main prey should be sought in variables like prey abundance, vulnerability, accessibility and environmental condition (Mech et al, 1998). Being the study not supported by a long-term historical data on both wolf diet and wild ungulate trend, to better understand the wolf feeding ecology in Romania, each variable was analyzed and discussed in the available literature:

1) ABUNDANCE: no differences were found regarding the prey abundance in PVS0 area. According to pellet group count data (WolfLife, unpublished data), the wild ungulate community was quite balanced through the study area (see Wild ungulate abundance), suggesting that prey abundance was not a relevant variable.

2) VULNERABILITY: in terms of “vulnerability” [i.e. *susceptibility to be injured or attacked*], the issue is more complex. Mech & Peterson (2003) mentioned twelve possible prey characteristics that may determinate vulnerability to wolves, factors such as sex, age, nutritional condition, weight, health condition, defenses and parental condition/age. Given that it is almost impossible to gather enough information to prove the conditions of preyed animals and by the fact that most of those are usually linked to specimen conditions, only the age, weight and defenses were taken into consideration.

To date, it is assumed that predators mainly prey on substandard individuals (weak, young, old, sick...). More specifically, the preference for a prey can be explained with the optimal foraging theory, which suggests that predators may select the most profitable prey, its profitability being measured as the ratio between energy gain and handling time (Stephens and Krebs, 1986). Young individuals generally represent a good compromise and even in the case of the wolf, it has been shown that juveniles (<1-year-old) actually compose a major part of its diet (Okarma 1995; Jędrzejewski et al, 2000; Mattioli et al, 2011). Among prey species, the wild boar has the highest proportion of young individuals in its population and newborns are scattered over a longer period. Moreover, in terms of optimal foraging theory, juveniles in the middle of their body growth up to sub-adult seem to be an optimal prey choice for the wolf (Mattioli et al, 2011). In comparison, the productivity of cervids is lower (2-3 fawns the roe deer, 1-2 the red deer) and the juveniles, resembling an adult in size already at the first winter, are able to easily move and escape even in deep snow. For those reasons, the advantage to hunt young wild boar rather than cervids may be significant over a winter.

Particular attention must be given as well to the defenses that animals have at their disposal. Although all young individuals lack in effective defenses and thus being potentially vulnerable, adult ungulates can defend themselves very effectively. An adult wild boar is in fact able to protect itself and occasionally it can also kill wolves (Vyrypaev, 1980). A stag, being provided with powerful antlers, if threatened could face few individuals or even a pack of wolves (Mech & Peterson, 2003). The roe deer, the smallest among the present ungulates, is actually the only one unable to stand against a wolf. Even so, being the wild boar potentially the heavier defenseless prey available (considering the juveniles), it seems once again the most profitable prey.

3) ACCESSIBILITY: being all the ungulates present in the same proportion in PVSO area, the prey “accessibility” [i.e. *easy to approach, reach or use; obtainable*], could be related to the use of space and prey behaviour, closely related to the detectability. In winter, both wild boar and red deer are highly gregarious species (compared to roe deer), forming often large herds and passing through the winter in group (Mustoni et al, 2002). In this period, the herds detectability is relatively high (Huggard, 1993; Hebblewhite & Pletscher 2002), foraging mostly in the same open areas (Huggard, 1993) and living in large mature forests (such those in Romania). Moreover, the sporadic presence of feeding point (used for game species) may work as point of attraction, making even more predictable the presence of some prey, mostly the generalist as the wild boar (Morimando et al, 2008). The roe deer, with its elusive and secretive lifestyle together with a lower aggregation rate, could be harder to find (Bongi et al, 2008) and thus a more difficult prey for wolf. Chamois, present at low densities in PVSO, was almost inaccessible by wolf due to its fragmented distribution, ecology and habitat use, explaining its absence in the diet. The prey accessibility could be also related to the number of hunting wolf in the pack. A large pack usually consume larger prey than a pair, which is forced to use a more limited spectrum due to their lower hunting efficiency (Mech & Boitani, 2003). The camera trapping and the snow-tracking sessions carried out during the winter showed that most of the time wolves were moving in pairs or in group of three, potentially explaining the low frequency of large prey like the red deer, virtually the lesser accessible in the study area. Given the similar abundance of wild ungulates, the accessibility of wild boar may be higher because of its behaviour (which makes it easily detectable) combined with its body mass (being a sub-adult also accessible by a single pair of wolves).

4) ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITION: as suggested by Okarma et al (1995), the snow cover and the temperature were considered as major environmental limitations for the ungulates during the winter. The wild boar, due to its physical structure (provided with short legs) and feeding ecology (rooting behaviour) it suffers much deep snow and frozen soil. During snowy and cold winters, wild boars starve, are victims of disease and die on mass. The cervids are generally less affect by it, suffering mostly during the prolonged period of very deep snow cover. Moreover, the effect of harsh winter may affect the prey nutrition, showing its effects even after generation or seasons (Mech & Peterson, 2003). Indicatively, a snow depth of >60-50 cm for the red deer, >50 cm for roe deer and >30-40 cm for wild boar could be a strong limitation for the prey species (Formozov, 1946). On the contrary, being the wolf much lighter than the large ungulates, in winters with deep snow, the limited prey mobility and the prey body condition lead to an increasing hunting success of wolf (Okarma 1995; Mech & Peterson, 2003).

After a critical analysis of the available literature, it seems that wild boar represents so far the best profitable prey in PVSO, being relatively easy to catch (both at younger ages or by a small wolf pack size), abundant (widespread and with the highest young / adults rate among wild ungulate species) and able to provide a large energy income (the average weight is three times greater than a roe deer and twice less than a red deer; Table 1). Conditions potentially favored by its accessibility (gregarious species in large mature

forests) and by snowy winters, in which the wild boar seems to suffer much more than the other prey species.

These assumptions are partially supported by [Sin et al \(2015\)](#) results, in which the wild boar appears more frequently in the diet (77% of BIO), while the other ungulates in a lesser extent than the present study (roe deer= 10%; red deer= 6%). Furthermore, in the same winter (2013/14) the wild boar was positively selected, the roe deer neither selected nor avoided and the red deer strongly avoided.

It should be pointed out that the wolf diet may show a shift from a prey to another because of seasonal/yearly changes in prey abundance and accessibility ([Meriggi et al, 1991](#); [Huggard 1993](#); [Mattioli et al, 2011](#); [Llaneza & López-Bao, 2015](#)), suggesting to consider the results as specific for the reference winter, characterized by certain prey abundance and climatic conditions. The recommendation is to focus the effort in a long-term study, measuring year to year all the already exposed variables and thus making it possible to observe a possible variation through the years.

WOLF DIET - OTHER PREY SPECIES

Even if livestock represent in different countries an important food source in the wolf diet ([Meriggi & Lovari, 1996](#); [Zlatanova et al, 2014](#)), its presence in the winter diet in PVS0 area is low (i.e. pig), probably due to “food caching” ([Mech, 1970](#)), a livestock depredation in a farm (in winter swine are generally confined in piggeries) or scavenging, being the livestock virtually not accessible in the study area in the reference season.

The dog, as shown by the previous work in the Putna Vrancea Natural Park ([Sin et al, 2015](#)), it constituted an important prey for wolf during the summer, being slightly used during winter up to be the second most frequent food item in the summer (12% of BIO). It is a complex ecological phenomenon occurring in different countries ([Butler et al, 2013](#)) and involving aspects of predation, defense and dominance ([Karlsson and Jaxgård, 2004](#)). Already addressed by several authors ([Lescureux & Linnell, 2014](#); [Butler et al, 2013](#)), it shows where the species are sympatric and the natural prey occurs at very low density (spatially and temporally), situations in which the extent of consumption may become considerable ([Pozio et al., 2001](#); [Sidorovich et al, 2003](#); [Llaneza & López-Bao, 2015](#)). In the PVS0 study area, being the wild ungulate community widespread but present at low density, the dog could be a potential replacement. Relative vulnerable prey, in winter it can be found at villages’ garbage dumps, as woodcutters’ pet ([Figure 16](#)) and to a lesser extent as free ranging dogs ([Rizzardini et al, 2015](#)), thus being accessible and virtually a profitable food item. In summer, being widely accessible (from the remote mountains to inhabited hilly areas) and abundant (sheepdogs), it is definitely one of the most profitable prey in the study area. Further study should include the dog consistency in the study area, to assess the dog selectivity and its importance in the wolf dietary habit in Romania.

The presence of a bear cub as food item sheds light on an aspect – the predation between large carnivores – rarely addressed by researchers ([Ballard et al, 2003](#)). Although few diets report black bear (*Ursus americanus*) in the diet ([Tremblay et al, 2001](#); [Darimont et al, 2004](#)), it seems that the presence of brown bear as food item it is a very rare event, so

far reported only in Turkey ([Capitani et al, 2015](#)) and Eastern Russia ([Miquelle et al, 2005](#)). Of unknown origin, the animal might have been actively hunted or died for other reasons. Further insights will be necessary on this issue. Due to the low presence in the wolf diet and considering their contribution not meaningful as food resources, the other species (e.g. *Mustelidae* and *Rodentia*) have not debated.

In conclusion, it is at least essential to remember once again the necessity of considering the data with caution, since the high confidence interval leaves a large degree of uncertainty in the interpretation of the data. Further analyses are definitely recommended, structuring the research in a long-term study, improving the study's weakness and including the prey structure (age classes) in the analysis.

- CHAPTER 2 -

WINTER SPATIAL INTERACTION BETWEEN WOLF (*Canis lupus*) AND LYNX (*Lynx lynx*)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SNOW-TRACKING SURVEY

In order to assess the winter spatial distribution of the two predators, the snow-tracking survey was carried out following the proposed experimental design, conceived to distribute the collection equally in terms of space and time (see Materials and Methods in Chapter 1). Performed over the winter semester, data collection was done exclusively on transects and when they were evenly covered by snow (at least 24 hours after the snowfall). The repetitions were made depending on the snow presence and to minimize the problem of non-independence of the data (Boitani & Powell, 2012), a time interval longer than one month was allowed to elapse between repetitions. For the purpose of the study only tracks were considered (Figure 17 & 18), being the probability to detect the other signs of presence (e.g. scats) highly dependent on the ecology of the species. Indeed, the lynx often buries the scats under the snow, soil or litter (Jędrzejewski & Sidorovich, 2010), making their finding much harder than those of wolf. Assuming that a single paw print found in the snow is insufficient for a clear and univocal identification, the tracks discrimination (namely wolf/lynx/dog) was done considering a conservative multicriteria approach (Harris & Ream, 1983; Ciucci, 2001; Jędrzejewski & Sidorovich, 2010). The size and shape (lynx paw prints are asymmetrical, generally clawless and smaller than the wolf's ones; those of a medium-large size dog are generally wolf-like; Figure 19), the overlapping (dogs rarely overlap), the behaviour (lynx and wolf tracks form a regular line, dog tracks instead are more dispersed and direction changes are frequent) and the location (e.g. near to a village, a sheepfold, logger's hut, etc) were considered as discriminating factors to classify the track. Once it was identified as wolf or lynx track, it was georeferenced with a handheld Global Positioning System (Garmin GPS 64s). Being the sampling effort transect-based (Campbell et al, 2008), each carnivore track was considered as a segment (thus associated with a linear measurement, e.g. 0,15 km), in which a single finding (e.g. a transect crossing or a single pawprint), was classified as 0,01 km considering the average GPS error. Each track was then considered as an independent observation in the sample of *used* (Manly et al, 2002). Data storage was done using DNRgps 6.1.0.6 (Minnesota Department of Natural Resources, 2015) and Microsoft Excel 2013. All the spatial analyses were conducted with QGIS 2.8.1 "Wien" (QGIS Development Team, 2015).

HABITAT SELECTION

According to the aim of the study, the data on resources availability and their use by animals were recorded at the population level (design I), in which the selection was defined comparing a sample of used resource with a census of available resource (protocol A) (Manly et al, 2002). The selection was defined following the assumptions

drawn by the authors: “There is no unique identification of data collected from different animals, the proportions of available units in different resource categories are known, and a random sample of used resource units is taken”. Thus, in order to assess the wolf and lynx habitat selection, a resource selection index (w_i) (Manly et al, 2002) was calculated:

$$w_i = \frac{o_i}{\pi_i}$$

where w_i is the selection rate, o_i the proportion of the sample of used resources units in the category i and π_i the proportion of available resources units in the category i . The index ranges from zero (negative selection) to infinity (positive selection), with 1 defining the value expected by chance (no selection). The proportion of *available* resources, namely the land use, was mapped using the Corine Land Cover 2012 dataset (Figure 7), with an accuracy (i.e. *Minimum Mapping Unit*) of 25 hectares for areal phenomena and 100 meters for linear phenomena (EEA, 2015). The proportion of *used* resources was defined overlapping the tracks found with the different habitat categories.

A useful way to present the results is to standardize the selection rate:

$$B_i = \frac{w_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

where B_i is the standardized selection index and the outcome (ranging from zero to one) gives the estimated probability that a used resource if randomly selected, would be in the category i if all the categories were equally frequent in the original population of available resources (Manly et al, 2002).

To measure the niche overlap, namely the habitat selection, the Pianka’s index was used (Pianka, 1973; Giraudoux, 2014):

$$O_{jk} = \frac{\sum_i^n p_{ij} p_{ik}}{\sqrt{\sum_i^n p_{ij}^2 \sum_i^n p_{ik}^2}}$$

where O_{jk} is the Pianka’s measure of niche overlap between species j and k , p_{ij} is the proportion of used resource i by the species j , p_{ik} is the proportion of used resource i by the species k and n the number of resources states. A symmetric measure of overlap, the result range from zero (no resources used in common) to one (resources were shared). The same analytical procedure was thus applied to assess the altitude selection. In the latter analysis, considering the topography of the PVS0 area and believing to be biologically more reliable, the available resources (namely the altitudinal isopleths) were grouped into three categories: *lowland* (ranging from 600 m a.s.l. and 899 m a.s.l.), *mid mountain* (ranging from 900 m a.s.l. and 1.199 m a.s.l.) and *ridge* (ranging from 1 200 m a.s.l. and 1.499 m a.s.l.). No category was assigned to the isopleths over 1.500 m a.s.l., since it was not possible to cover those areas in winter. With the assumption of no selection, the Log-likelihood ratio (G-test) test of independence (Sokal & Rohlf, 1981; Hurd, 2001) was used to statistically test both the habitat and the altitude selection.

TEMPORAL AND SPATIAL OVERLAP

In order to evaluate the overlap between the carnivores, the transects were split into 250m, 500m and 1km trail segments and the presence/absence of both species was calculated in each section using the snow-tracking data (Figure 4). Hence to assess the temporal and the spatial overlap, two different approaches were used. Temporally, the analysis was carried out considering each snow survey independently, wherein only the tracks found in a specific session were compared. Spatially, the comparison was made considering all the tracks, as a result of the superimposition from each repetition. A binary code was used to define the presence (1) and the absence (0) and contingency tables were built for each scenario. Because the monitoring was based on maximizing the wolf's signs of presence encounter, the difference between the segments with only lynx (i.e. lynx/No wolf) and those with both carnivores (i.e. lynx/wolf) was tested. Thus, a *degree of avoidance* ($Lynx\ occupancy / Lynx \wedge Wolf\ occupancy$) in temporal and spatial overlap was also calculated, which results ranged from one (no avoidance) to infinity (avoidance). The Log-likelihood ratio (G-test) test of independence (Sokal & Rohlf, 1981; Hurd, 2001) was used to statistically test the overlap of tracks ($H_0 =$ tracks overlap; $H_1 =$ tracks do not overlap). All statistical analysis were carried out with R 3.0.3 "Warm puppy" (R core team, 2014).

FIGURE 4 – Example of tracks overlap assessment using the 1km trail segment. The temporal overlap takes into account each snow survey independently while the spatial overlap considers all the tracks, as a result of the superimposition from each repetition. A binary code was used to define the presence (1) and the absence (0) **Lynx occupancy / Wolf occupancy*.

RESULTS

The study area was surveyed over 119 days of consecutive snow cover (from December to March) using transects (n= 57) of different lengths (\bar{x} = 9.173 km \pm 4.056 km). Of these, 47% were performed once, 31% twice and 22% three times, covering a total length of 522,9 km. With the exception of the south-central part of PVS0 (see Discussion in Chapter 1), all the square were covered during the snow period and the transects were evenly distributed in all the study area. A total of 35,60 km of wolf tracks (n= 69) and 6,02 km of lynx tracks (n= 48) were found (Figure 5).

FIGURE 5 – The distribution of transects and tracks found (from both wolf and lynx) during the winter 2014/15 in PVS0 area. The square codes (e.g. 10km E557 N269) are shown in the grid.

In the PVS0 area, the available resources were composed by pasture (CLC code= 231), land occupied by agriculture (243), broad-leaved forest (311), coniferous forest (312), mixed forest (313), natural grasslands (321) and transitional woodland-shrub (324). Out of seven different habitats, both species completely avoided the pastures and the land occupied by agriculture. Among the used habitats, the wolf showed a positive selection for broad-leaved forest ($w_i = 1,54$), natural grasslands ($w_i = 1,62$) and transitional woodland-shrub ($w_i = 1,49$). Lynx, likewise, selected natural grasslands ($w_i = 1,53$) and transitional woodland-shrub ($w_i = 1,30$). However, using the standardized selection index (B_i), the values appeared to be very similar, suggesting for both species a random use of the resources (Table 4). Indeed, the difference on used habitat was not significant (Wolf: $G = 2,4652$, $df = 6$, $p\text{-value} = n.s.$; Lynx: $G = 4,1309$, $df = 6$, $p\text{-value} = n.s.$). A strong similarity in habitat use was also showed between predators (Graph 4) which seemed to share greatly the available resources across the PVS0 (Pianka's index, $O = 0,97$).

CLC class	% available	WOLF				LYNX			
		u_i	% used	w_i	B_i	u_i	% used	w_i	B_i
231	0,02	0 (0)	0	0	0	0 (0)	0	0	0
243	0,003	0 (0)	0	0	0	0 (0)	0	0	0
311	0,15	8.130 (14)*	0,23	1,54	0,25	950 (8)	0,16	1,07	0,19
312	0,20	5.880 (17)	0,17	0,82	0,13	830 (11)	0,14	0,68	0,12
313	0,51	15.010 (43)	0,42	0,83	0,13	3.220 (21)	0,54	1,05	0,19
321	0,07	3.860 (7)	0,11	1,62	0,26	620 (8)	0,10	1,54	0,27
324	0,05	2.720 (7)	0,08	1,49	0,24	400 (5)	0,07	1,31	0,23
Total	1	35.600 (88)	1	6,30	1	6.020 (53)	1	5,64	1

TABLE 4 – Habitat selection of both wolf and lynx in the Eastern Carpathians (PVS0 area), Romania in 2014/15. In the table the meters of track found for each land cover class (u_i), the selection index (w_i) and the standardized selection index (B_i) are shown. *In brackets the number of tracks per habitat.

GRAPH 4 – The standardized selection index (B_i) for each type of habitats and for both predators. On the X axis the CLC classes are shown (Figure 7).

Regarding the selection among altitudes the species used, to differing degrees, all the available ranges (from the lowlands to the highest portion monitored). In detail, wolf selected ridges ($w_i = 1,50$), randomly used lowland ($w_i = 0,91$) and mid mountain ($w_i = 0,95$). Conversely, lynx almost avoided low altitudes ($w_i = 0,41$), occasionally selected ridges ($w_i = 1,26$) and preferred the mid mountain ($w_i = 1,61$) (Table 5; Graph 5). The results were emphasized by the standardized selection index (B_i), in which the most used resources were selected with an estimated probability of nearly 50 % (Wolf: $B_{high} = 0,45$; Lynx $B_{med} = 0,49$) (Table 5). According to the Log-likelihood ratio test of independence, there was not significant difference in the wolf selection ($G = 0,8240$, $df = 2$, $p\text{-value} = n.s.$), while the difference was significant in the case of the lynx ($G = 6,3397$, $df = 2$, $p\text{-value} < 0,05$). The latter result showed an effective selection of mid mountain by the felids and a consequent avoidance of lowlands. Finally, despite the slight difference in altitudinal selection, the species showed a high level of niche overlap considering the altitudinal ranges (Pianka's index, $O = 0,83$).

Alt.*	% available	WOLF				LYNX			
		u_i	% used	w_i	B_i	u_i	% used	w_i	B_i
Low	0,46	14.950 (30)	0,42	0,91	0,27	1.220 (11)	0,20	0,41	0,13
Med	0,42	14.240 (34)	0,40	0,95	0,28	3.920 (32)	0,65	1,61	0,49
High	0,12	6.410 (12)	0,18	1,50	0,45	880 (5)	0,15	1,26	0,38
Total	1	35.600 (76)	1	3,36	1	6.020 (48)	1	3,28	1

TABLE 5 – Altitude selection of both wolf and lynx in the Eastern Carpathians (PVSO area), Romania in 2014/15. In the table the meters of track found (no.) for each altitudinal category (u_i), the selection index (w_i) and the standardized selection index (B_i) are shown. * Low= Lowland; Med= Mid mountain; High= Ridge.

GRAPH 5 – The selection index (w_i) for each altitudinal class and for both predators. The altitudinal ranges are shown in meters.

In total, the wolf tracks were detected in 9,71% (250m), 11,76% (500m) and 16,48% (1km) of segments considering the temporal occupancy and in 14,63%, 16,94% and 24,17% of segments considering the spatial occupancy. Fewer lynx tracks were found during the monitoring, since in terms of temporal occupancy it was detected in 3,20%, 5,26% and 9,20% of segments and spatially in 4,95%, 7,87% and 11,78% of segments. Regarding the *degree of avoidance*, in terms of temporal occupancy, lynx seemed to avoid the wolf considering all the segment, while spatially, the species shared the territory over a 500m radius (Table 6; Graph 6). These findings were supported by the G-test (log likelihood ratio test of independence):

- Temporally, there was a clear species avoidance in all segments: 250m ($G = 43,5484$, $df = 1$, $p\text{-value} < 0,0001$), 500m ($G = 21,0109$, $df = 1$, $p\text{-value} < 0,0001$) and 1 km ($G = 10,3619$, $df = 1$, $p\text{-value} < 0,001$).
- Spatially, there was avoidance within both 250m ($G = 10,7898$, $df = 1$, $p\text{-value} < 0,001$) and 500m segments ($G = 4,9562$, $df = 1$, $p\text{-value} > 0,01$), but not within 1 km trail segments ($G = 0,2281$, $df = 1$, $p\text{-value} > 0,5$).

	segment	Temporal			Spatial		
		No Wolf	Wolf	<i>Avoidance</i>	No Wolf	Wolf	<i>Avoidance</i>
Lynx	250m	59	8	7,38 (***)	45	19	2,37 (**)
	500m	44	11	4,00 (***)	34	18	1,89 (*)
	1km	35	13	2,69 (**)	21	18	1,17 (n.s.)

TABLE 6 - Absolute frequency of temporal and spatial segment occupancy in the Eastern Carpathians (PVSO area), Romania in 2014/15. The *degree of avoidance* is also shown. * $0,05 > p > 0,01$; ** $p < 0,001$; *** $p < 0,0001$; (n.s.) not significant.

GRAPH 6 - Graphical representation of the *degree of avoidance* in temporal and spatial overlap.

DISCUSSION

SNOW-TRACKING SURVEY

The snow tracking survey represents a valuable method to study secretive and elusive species such as large carnivores (Špinkytė-Bačkaitienė, 2005; Sand et al, 2006; see review in Whittington et al, 2015). Largely used in field studies, it is frequently combined with occupancy models (see review in Whittington et al, 2015). Despite these allow making assumptions about the detection process, the inference based on replication strictly requires that replicates must be selected randomly and with replacement. The application of the specific experimental designs requires a considerable research effort and a high investment of resources, not always affordable in a wildlife management project. The proposed method should be seen as a cost-effective alternative, able to define the environmental requirements of a species in the early stages of a project. Spatially, the area was properly covered with a network of transects as evenly distributed as possible, covering all the available habitats and altitudinal range proposed (except above 1.500 m a.s.l, see Materials and Methods in Chapter 2). Similar conclusions, already exposed in the previous section, were drawn for the low species abundance in certain localities of the study area (see Discussion in Chapter 1). Temporally, the effort to minimize the problem of non-independence of the data (Boitani & Powell, 2012) was achieved too. With four consecutive months of snow cover, the time interval was large enough to allow a second and a third repetition of some transects, thus enabling a stronger inference regarding the obtained results. Unfortunately, despite the large effort applied in the whole study area (552 km entirely covered by feet), the number of lynx tracks found were not particularly numerous. The explanation may be found in its solitary lifestyle and the large home-range that leads to natural lower abundance, which might explain the lower encounter rate. However, since the data were well distributed in space and time, the sample was considered appropriate for the final analysis.

HABITAT SELECTION

The lack of significant habitat selection by the predators basically shows their ubiquitous behavior. The wolf is in fact a ubiquitous species, reported living in forests and prairies, ranging from tundra, barren ground, mountains, deserts, swamps and even peri-urban areas (Mech & Boitani, 2003). The lynx, however, is generally more linked to forests, although it preferred landscape heterogeneity instead of large wooded areas (Linnell et al, 2001; Zimmermann and Breitenmoser, 2002; Niedziałkowska et al, 2006; Basille et al, 2009). In PVS0 area both predators showed a preference for the transitional woodland-shrub and open area, with a use of forest in proportion to the availability and a complete avoidance of the pastures and land occupied by agriculture. None of the avoided habitats were taken in particular consideration hereafter since their frequency in the territory

slightly exceed the 2%. Their avoidance might be the result of both inadequate sampling or an effective lack of species in those areas. Concerning those selected, the reasons for their use were sought in the available literature, since no systematic study has been done in Romania before.

The presence of a predator in a certain environment is mostly influenced by prey distribution (Miquelle et al, 1999; Fuller et al, 2003; McLoughlin et al, 2004; Oakleaf et al, 2006; Basille et al, 2009). Natural grasslands and transitional woodland-shrub attract all species of ungulates, from selectors to grass eaters (Hofmann, 1989), thus acting as hotspots. The wild prey encounters is in fact relatively high in the open areas (Huggard, 1993; Hebblewhite & Pletscher 2002), whereas transitional woodland-shrub could be selected because it is an important habitat both for hunting (given the presence of roe deer: Myrnerud and Østbye, 1995; Ratikainen et al, 2007) and resting (Sunde et al, 1998; Špinkytė-Bačkaitienė, 2005). Moreover, being the predators in winter not bound to particular areas (e.g. den or rendezvous site), most movements within the home range are done to maximize the prey encounter, thus explaining the higher use of such habitats. Their ecological role is even greater if combined with forest patch. The habitat diversity provides the so-called “edge effect”: an ecotone between two habitats frequently contains at least some species from each habitat plus some species not typically found in either (Odum & Barret, 2004). Given the presence of large and continuous mature forests in PVS0 area, the carnivores could gain advantaged from this ecological complexity, being able to satisfy several biological needs (hunting, resting, sheltering, etc) during their daily activities. The result basically would show that in very homogenous areas, as the large Romanian forests, the species may look for the most heterogeneous areas.

Although any of those categories were significantly selected by predators, these preliminary results have shed light once again on the possible importance of environmental complexity, laying the foundation for future long-term studies based on gps-tracking.

ALTITUDE SELECTION

The wolf, compared to the lynx, seems to use more the highest portion of the PVS0. Due to its territoriality, in terms of cost-efficiency, it usually uses the main ridge both for fast movement inside its territory (Mech & Boitani, 2003) and to maximize the marking behaviour (Zub et al, 2003). The highest density of marks is observed in the centre (mostly in summertime) and in hotspots places along the edges of the wolf pack territories (Gosling & Roberts, 2001; Zub et al, 2003). Being the wolves' home ranges often shaped by morphological features (Mech & Boitani, 2003), the main ridges most likely represent potential boundaries among packs. This hypothesis was supported by results obtained from the genetic analysis (WolfLife, unpublished data), which showed that genotypes from individuals of different packs were clustered according to the main mountainous reliefs. The random use of the other altitudinal ranges does nothing but confirm the wolf's plasticity, capable of benefiting from a wide range of environmental conditions (Mech & Boitani, 2003).

The lynx selection pattern was instead driven by an effective avoidance of the lowland, since both middle mountain and ridges were positively selected. The PVS0 is a quite remote area in which the inhabitants live almost exclusively in the lower portions (INS, 2011b). Despite the current literature have shown that the predator can adapt to human-influenced environments if its favourite prey is found in those areas (Basille et al, 2009, 2013; Bouyer et al, 2014, 2015), the human activities and the presence of a large number of dogs next to the villages (WolfLife, 2015) most likely provide disturbance to both predator and preys, which can dispose of large less-disturbed areas to live in. Moreover, in winter, the most productive areas for ungulates are found in the middle mountain, where a considerable amount of food it is made available by forestry activities (Cutini et al, 2011). Strongly linked to prey presence (Basille et al, 2009) and to forested areas (Linnell et al, 2001; Zimmermann and Breitenmoser, 2002; Niedziałkowska et al, 2006; Basille et al, 2009), the middle mountain may be the most suitable range for the lynx, while the ridges could represent, as for the wolf, the boundaries for the territories of different animals.

SPECIES OVERLAP

Despite the large use of 1-km trail segment in studies of occupancy (Hines et al, 2010; Mordecai et al, 2011; Thorn et al, 2011; Whittington et al, 2015), for the purpose of this study, a wider range of segments were chosen to better assess the spatial overlap. The choice was made trying to understand how the degree of avoidance varies with the length of segments, thus supporting a more accurate assessment on use of space by both predators. This allows indeed to state that the species spatially share territory, over a 500m radius, but not temporally, suggesting that both carnivores use the same trails but at different times.

Snow-tracking data from several studies (see review in Schmidt et al, 2009) and data on radio-collared animals (Schmidt et al, 2009; Wikenros et al, 2010; Kusak et al, 2013) support those findings, showing that carnivores tend to share their territories, neither avoiding nor attracting each other. The explanation lies in the factors driving the ecological interaction, in which the most common is probably the competition (Ballard et al, 2003). To coexist in the same territory, two competing species should avoid any form of competition, which it is made possible by a niche differentiation (Krebs, 1994). A number of aspects such as diet, life habits and habitat use may further ease resource partitioning (Schmidt et al, 2009). It would seem that in a community of carnivores, the niches differentiation is mainly based on different feeding ecology (Jędrzejewska & Jędrzejewski, 1998). This can be easily demonstrate by the fact that the lynx shows a specialization on roe deer in large part of its range (Pulliainen, 1981; Okarma et al, 1997; Jobin et al, 2000; Valdmann et al, 2005; Sidorovich, 2006; Krofel et al, 2011), assuming thus a similar eating behaviour in Romania, while wolf fed primarily on wild boar and partially on wild cervids (see Results in Chapter 1). Furthermore, due to their solitary lifestyle, felids have adapted to a stalking-hunting, while canids, living in well-structured packs, make the coursing-hunting behaviour their strength (Kleiman & Eisenberg, 1973;

Husseman et al, 2003). These different evolutionary strategies allow the species to focus their hunting on different prey, thereby maintaining separate ecological niches. This assumption is also supported by their habitat selection in PVS0. Since the species share the areas with same land cover, the temporal shift in their use appear to be crucial for their “peaceful coexistence” (*in sensu* Major & Sherburne, 1987), which might allow predators to perform their vital functions minimizing the phenomena of competition. Most likely the differences in diet, habitat use (in temporal terms) and hunting behavior all contribute to allow the wolf and lynx coexistence wherever habitat and available prey resources fulfill both predators’ requirements (Schmidt et al, 2009). In the near future, it would be suggested this short-term study is developed with radio-gps tracking to gather a medium-long term understanding of the wolf-lynx relationship.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 – LABORATORY FORM

WOLF WINTER DIET (2014/2015) - LABORATORY FORM					
FIELD COD: _____		DATE: _____			
LAB CODE: _____					
OPERATORS: _____					
FUR					
Food items	% of occurrence				
	6-25	26-50	51-75	76-100	
Wild ungulates:					
Wild boar					
Red deer					
Roe deer					
Cervids ind.					
Chamois					
Meso-Micro mammals:					
Hare					
Mustelids					
Microrodents					
Livestock:					
Sheep					
Goat					
Cattle					
Horse					
Other items:					
Fruit/Vegetable					
Food items	Age				
	Fur			Bones	
	Young ($\leq 1y$)	Adult ($> 1y$)	Fur coat (summer/winter)	Young ($< 1y$)	Adult ($> 1y$)

FIGURE 6 – Laboratory form used during the scat washing procedure.

ANNEX 2 – CORINE LAND COVER (CLC) LEGEND

1. Artificial surfaces

1.1 Urban fabric

- 1.1.1. Continuous urban fabric
- 1.1.2. Discontinuous urban fabric

1.2 Industrial, commercial and transport units

- 1.2.1. Industrial or commercial units
- 1.2.2. Road and rail networks and associated land
- 1.2.3. Port areas
- 1.2.4. Airports

1.3 Mine, dump and construction sites

- 1.3.1. Mineral extraction sites
- 1.3.2. Dump sites
- 1.3.3. Construction sites

1.4 Artificial, non-agricultural vegetated areas

- 1.4.1. Green urban areas
- 1.4.2. Sport and leisure facilities

2. Agricultural areas

2.1 Arable land

- 2.1.1. Non-irrigated arable land
- 2.1.2. Permanently irrigated land
- 2.1.3. Rice fields

2.2 Permanent crops

- 2.2.1. Vineyards
- 2.2.2. Fruit trees and berry plantations
- 2.2.3. Olive groves

2.3 Pastures

- 2.3.1. Pastures

2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas

- 2.4.1. Annual crops associated with permanent crops
- 2.4.2. Complex cultivation patterns
- 2.4.3. Land principally occupied by agriculture
- 2.4.4. Agro-forestry areas

3. Forest and seminatural areas

3.1 Forests

- 3.1.1. Broad-leaved forest
- 3.1.2. Coniferous forest
- 3.1.3. Mixed forest

3.2 Shrub and/or herbaceous vegetation associations

- 3.2.1. Natural grassland
- 3.2.2. Moors and heathland
- 3.2.3. Sclerophyllous vegetation
- 3.2.4. Transitional woodland shrub

3.3 Open spaces with little or no vegetation

- 3.3.1. Beaches, dunes, and sand plains
- 3.3.2. Bare rock
- 3.3.3. Sparsely vegetated areas
- 3.3.4. Burnt areas
- 3.3.5. Glaciers and perpetual snow

4. Wetlands

4.1 Inland wetlands

- 4.1.1. Inland marshes
- 4.1.2. Peat bogs

4.2 Coastal wetlands

- 4.2.1. Salt marshes
- 4.2.2. Salines
- 4.2.3. Intertidal flats

5. Water bodies

5.1 Inland waters

- 5.1.1. Water courses
- 5.1.2. Water bodies

5.2 Marine waters

- 5.2.1. Coastal lagoons
- 5.2.2. Estuaries
- 5.2.3. Sea and ocean

FIGURE 7 - Retrieved from <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/corine-land-cover-2006-by-country/legend>.

ANNEX 3 – PHOTOGRAPHIC DOCUMENTATION

Figure 8 – Overview of the PVS0 study area. © Andrea Corradini

Figure 9 – Lynx on a red deer carcass camera-trapped in the PVS0 study area.
© WOLFLIFE

Figure 10 – Adult bear camera-trapped in the PVS0 study area. © WOLFLIFE

Figure 11 – Wolf excrement. © Andrea Corradini

Figure 12 – Washing procedure. © National Geographic Romania

Figure 13 – Washed sample stapled to the laboratory form and samples in slide ready to be analyzed. © Andrea Corradini

Figure 14 – Pellet group count survey (strip census with the aid of a rope). © Guido Rastrelli

Figure 15 – Severe snow condition in the higher portion of the study area (1.700 m a.s.l.). © Andrea Corradini

Figure 16 – Loggers' caravan used in winter during the cutting season. The workers (at that time they were working in the forest) are often accompanied by dogs. © Andrea Corradini

Figure 17 – Snow tracking session (in the picture a wolf track). © Andrea Corradini

Figure 18 - Lynx track. © Andrea Corradini

Figure 19 - Wolf and lynx pawprints. © Andrea Corradini